

ISI5302: OpenAlex Evaluation
Level 0 - Art

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1. Introduction

OpenAlex is an online repository with over 243 million works, of which 43 million are open access. It uses an automated tagging system to classify these works. The system is “fully open: built on open-source code, using open models, and distributed via an open data dump and open API” (Automated concept tagging for OpenAlex, n.d., p. 2). The system’s structure uses a five-level system to categorise concepts: Level 0 (L0), Level 1 (L1), Level 2 (L2), Level 3 (L3), Level 4 (L4), Level 5 (L5). L0 or the “root level” has nineteen concepts.

The objective of this report is to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the OpenAlex automated classification system by analysing the structure under the root level concept *Art*. Our multifaceted approach includes (1) a literature review and environmental scan that further explains how OpenAlex works and how it is being used; (2) a qualitative analysis that assesses the hierarchical and semantic quality of the system; (3) a quantitative analysis that assesses the amount of concepts per level, the concept distribution, and the relevance of concepts in relation to their parent concept; and (4) an evaluation of indexing that compares OpenAlex concept tagging to Library of Congress Subject Headings, with an assessment of the quality of concept tagging done by OpenAlex’s automated system.

While OpenAlex currently exists as an extensive repository for open access works and as a fully open classification system, our report highlights the necessity for significant restructuring and quality control. This is essential to build it into a system that accurately represents the diversity of works housed under *Art* and can be used effectively for research purposes. Our recommendations for improvement include a restructuring of the concepts, the removal of unuseful index terms, and verification that definitions are present and accurate. We also recommend that OpenAlex implements clear procedures in the case of synonymy and homonymy to omit related classification errors.

2. Literature review and environmental scan

OpenAlex is a resource provided by the non-profit organisation OurResearch. It uses the dataset from Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG), which was retired at the end of 2021, to provide free data describing scholarly entities and how those entities are connected to each other (Overview, n.d.). These entities include works, authors, sources, institutions, concepts, publishers, and funders, which together, form a heterogeneous directed graph of the entities and the connections between them (Overview, n.d.). Concepts, the focus of this paper, are index terms applied to works in OpenAlex.

There are many studies on how OpenAlex compares to Web of Science and Scopus, and it is well known for its comprehensive coverage of publications (Jiao et al., 2023). OpenAlex indexed more than 239 million works, with 50 thousand added daily (Okamura, 2023). It also indexes all the information related to the publication, such as author, institution, and language, demonstrating the sheer comprehensiveness of the database. OpenAlex pulls its data from places such as WikiData, Open Researcher and Contributor ID, the Research

Organization Register, PubMed, amongst many other institutional repositories. Compared to other databases, OpenAlex covers many disciplines and is completely open access. However, OpenAlex demands considerable effort from users, whether it be through filtering or reorganisation of data at the micro level (Okamura, 2023). For example, Laakso (2023) notes that OpenAlex requires a lot of filtering in order to narrow down specific information relating to the document type “books,” suggesting that it is not a straightforward or user-friendly database to interact with.

OpenAlex was described by representatives from OurResearch as a “drop-in replacement” for Microsoft Academic, offering a fully open source of scholarly metadata, including open data, an open API, and open source code (Priem et al., 2022). Hug et al. (2017) criticised the MAG Fields of Study (the MAG equivalent of concepts) as too specific, and mentioned that the hierarchies are incoherent, an issue that this paper will explore in OpenAlex’s concepts. When migrating from MAG to OpenAlex, the same taxonomy was used with a reduced number of Fields of Study, and concepts with less than 500 papers associated with them were removed (OpenAlex, 2021). OpenAlex V2 uses text from paper titles, as well as abstracts, to determine the assigned concepts (OpenAlex, 2021). Scheidsteger and Haunschild (2023) discuss the changes in the amount of concepts at each level during the migration from MAG to OpenAlex. While the 19 L0 concepts stayed the same, and only 8 L1 concepts were removed, less than 10% of the amount of concepts in L3 to L5 remained after the migration, and in L2, 15.62% remained. However, in both MAG and OpenAlex, L3 was found to have the highest number of terms, meaning that granularity does not necessarily increase with each level. In addition, OpenAlex assigns a larger number of concepts to works than MAG. The total coverage of works with assigned concepts increased from 74.6% to 86.6%, and the number of assignments per work to a top-level concept increased from 147 million papers in MAG to approximately 171 million papers in OpenAlex (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023). Notably, *Art* had the strongest increase in works assigned to it out of all the L0 concepts, with an increase of 2.22% (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023). However, the increased number of works assigned to the *Art* concept does not necessarily indicate that they were correctly assigned to it, as there is a great variance in accuracy for works assigned to art concepts.

Okamura (2023) situates OpenAlex within the wider landscape of an exponentially growing amount of science and technology data, and increasing demand for bibliometric analysis as bibliometricians collaborate more with science and technology policy makers (2023). He refers to Open Bibliometrics as part of a growing momentum of Open Science and Data Science, where tools like OpenAlex can be used to ensure the transparency and reproducibility of data analysis research (2023). Indeed, the database is popular amongst researchers due to its open access and large amount of data (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023). Researchers noted the ease in retrieving metadata as well as the accessibility of information available to researchers (Velez-Estevez et al., 2023), and noted that tools for analysing reference information are typically part of a paid database or behind a paywall, making OpenAlex an attractive option for this kind of work (Schaes & Mierz, 2023).

For example, researchers have shown interest in exploring the linked data relationship between OpenAlex and Wikidata, comparing Wikipedia page views of a topic with the corresponding number of works assigned to a concept in OpenAlex in an attempt to compare social popularity with academic interest in various topics (Arroyo-Machado & Costas, 2023). Ismail et al. used a similar method to compare Wikipedia page views and the number of works tagged with specific concepts related to a particular field (Ismail et al., 2023). However, as this paper will explore, scholars should exercise caution in this approach as works may not always be tagged with accurate or relevant concepts.

Some researchers noted inconsistencies in OpenAlex's metadata, such as errors in the open access status of works (Jahn et al., 2023), while others successfully used OpenAlex in conjunction with other databases to obtain information about open access books, noting some limitations, such as the lack of accuracy when filtering records classified as "books" (Laakso, 2023). Similarly, scholars found irregularities with document type metadata (Jiao et al., 2023), while others noted gaps in a lack of institutional metadata for dataset authors (Krause & Mongeon, 2023). Schares and Mierz, however, were able to successfully analyse institution-specific data using Python and Jupyter Notebooks with OpenAlex, without noting any specific limitations to their project (2023). Okamura notes a potential disadvantage of OpenAlex as "not distinguishing research outputs in different formats, such as treating an article the same way as a dataset or book when counting outputs," (Okamura, 2023, p.4). Indeed, papers from Jiao et al. and Krause and Mongeon found metadata limitations while working with datasets in OpenAlex in particular. These metadata limitations extend to OpenAlex's art concepts, which contain errors in their definitions, illogical hierarchies, and are often incorrectly assigned to works.

3. Evaluation

3.1 Evaluation of the classification system

This evaluation of OpenAlex as a classification system takes a multifaceted approach, analysing its concepts and concept levels (1) qualitatively, with attention to hierarchical and semantic issues; (2) quantitatively, with attention to concept distribution and relevance of concepts; and (3) by evaluating how concepts are applied for indexing of works. Our findings identify a range of shortcomings that ultimately negatively impact OpenAlex's retrieval accuracy.

3.1.a Qualitative Evaluation

A qualitative analysis of the OpenAlex system identifies hierarchical and semantic challenges. An assessment of this system is performed herein by analysing (1) the semantic and hierarchical correlation between L0 and L1 concepts, (2) the semantic and hierarchical correlation between L1, L2, and L3 concepts, (3) the overall quality of the hierarchical structure, and (4) the semantic challenges posed by inaccurate or unavailable definitions of

concepts. Our findings demonstrate that OpenAlex is not an effective indexing system. Suggestions to address these issues are provided throughout.

The relationship between the parent concept *Art-L0* and its six L1 children (*Classics*, *Humanities*, *Visual art*, *Art history*, *Literature*, *Aesthetics*) poses a set of challenges that impacts all lower levels. Important to the assessment of these relationships is an understanding of how these child concepts are defined by OpenAlex, and the quality of their semantic relationship to their parent concept. Presented below are definitions for *Art-L0* and its L1 children, alongside ratings of Excellent, Great, or Okay. The definitions were found using [https://api.openalex.org/concepts/\[ENTER CONCEPT ID\]](https://api.openalex.org/concepts/[ENTER CONCEPT ID]).

Excellent = explicit and clear relationship to parent concept based on definitions provided Great = implicit but clear relationship to parent concept based on definitions provided Okay = relationship between concepts exists, but needs to be reassessed and reordered		
L0		
Art	“expressive work intended to be appreciated for its beauty or emotional power; or the process of creating such a work.” (OpenAlex API, n.d.)	
L1		Quality of relationship to parent + justification
Classics	“study of classical antiquity such as ancient Greece and ancient Rome.” (OpenAlex API, n.d.)	Okay: refers to historical period
Humanities	“academic disciplines that study human culture.” (OpenAlex API, n.d.)	Okay: is broader than art
Visual Art	“art form which creates works that are primarily visual in nature” (OpenAlex API, n.d.)	Excellent: is “expressive work”
Art History	“academic study of objects of art in their historical development” (OpenAlex API, n.d.)	Great: study of “the process of creating such a work”
Literature	“polysemous term referring to a written art form, and the set of literary work” (OpenAlex API, n.d.)	Excellent: is “expressive work”
Aesthetics	“branch of philosophy dealing with the nature of art, beauty, and taste” (OpenAlex API, n.d.)	Great: study of “the process of creating such a work”

Table 01

As highlighted above, *Humanities-L1* is too broad of a concept to be found under *Art-L0*. Conversely, *Classics-L1*, referring to a historical period, does not correlate clearly with *Art-L0* based on the definitions provided. While it is related in the sense that “expressive work (...) or the process of creating such a work” existed in classical antiquity, it would be better suited elsewhere in the hierarchy.

It is equally important to evaluate the shared parents of these L1 concepts. As shown in **Figure 1.0**, *Aesthetics-L1* and *Humanities-L1* are also found under *Philosophy-L0*, while *Art history-L1* and *Classics-L1* are also found under *History-L0*. *Literature-L1* and *Visual art-L1* do not share parent concepts. Observing the L2 concepts found under these six L1 concepts demonstrates the discrepancies apparent in these hierarchical connections. For

example, while *Literature-L1* is not also classified under *Philosophy-L0*, it contains *Ancient philosophy-L2*, *Philosophy and literature-L2*, *Philosophy of love-L2*, and several other philosophy-related L2 concepts. Due to this, it seems beneficial to classify Literature under both *Art-L0* and *Philosophy-L0*.

Figure 1.0 Current Structure of Concepts, L0 to L1

In a similar realm, the scope of L1 concepts under *Art-L0* is limiting. This is apparent in the classification of dance, theatre, and music-related concepts under the existing L1 concepts. For example, *Music education-L2*, *Music festival-L2*, and *Musicology-L2* are classified under *Visual art-L1*. *Dance-L2*, *Waltz-L2*, and *Burlesque-L2* are also classified under *Visual art-L1*. Similarly, *Drama-L2*, *Dramatisation-L2*, and *Dramaturgy-L2* are classified under *Literature-L1*. Considering that dance, music, and theatre are generally considered to be equal to visual art as an “expressive work intended to be appreciated for its beauty or emotional power,” (OpenAlex), it would be beneficial to have this reflected in the system.

Figure 1.1 demonstrates a possible alternative structuring that considers the previously mentioned points, notably: (1) *Humanities-L1* being too broad in scope implies that it should be found earlier in the hierarchy, hence it becomes the L0 concept and *Philosophy*, *Art*, and *History* become the L1 concepts; (2) *Theatre*, *Dance*, and *Music* are added as L2 concepts on par with *Visual art*; (3) *Classics*, as it is a period in time rather than a domain or theory, becomes an L3 concept that exists under multiple L2 concepts.

Figure 1.1 Suggested Structure of Concepts, L0 to L3

While this alternative structuring places *Classics-L1* under both *Art history-L1* and *Literature*, there is an argument to be made that classics as “the study of classical antiquity” (OpenAlex) correlates to more than the two domains in which it has been placed. This brings forward another issue: OpenAlex does not seem to have a predefined method for discerning how the hierarchical assignment happens. This is identifiable in the correlations between L2 and L3 concepts. **Figure 2.0** presents the current structure, from *Classics-L1* to *Byzantine studies-L3*. Logically, *Byzantine architecture-L2* should be classified under *Byzantine studies-L3* because the architecture of a geographical region is reflective of studying the region. This change is reflected in **Figure 2.1**. Similarly, *Modern art-L3* and *Contemporary art-L3* are classified under *Performance art-L2*, as seen in **Figure 3.0**. Since *Modern art-L3* and *Contemporary art-L3* are wider in scope than *Performance art-L2*, it would be more logical for the structure to follow the hierarchy presented in **Figure 3.1**, where *Performance art* is the L3 concept and is classified under both *Modern art* and *Contemporary art*.

Figure 2.0 (Above) Current Correlation Between *Byzantine Architecture* and *Byzantine Studies*
Figure 2.1 (Below) Suggested Correlation Between *Byzantine Architecture* and *Byzantine Studies*

Figure 3.0 (Above) Current correlation between *Performance Art-L1*, *Modern Art-L2*, *Contemporary Art-L3*

Figure 3.1 (Below) Suggested Correlation Between *Performance Art-L1*, *Modern Art-L2*, *Contemporary Art-L3*

Similarly, there is no consistency in the types of concepts classified under the same level, made apparent by sampling five L3 concepts classified under *Art history-L1* (**Table 02**). This begs the question on whether, for example, a time period in art – which is broad and can include different types of art objects, theories, and movements – should be classified on the same level as a physical structure (such as an altar). The definitions were found using [https://api.openalex.org/concepts/\[ENTER CONCEPT ID\]](https://api.openalex.org/concepts/[ENTER CONCEPT ID]).

Concept	Definition	Concept Type
Aestheticism	"art movement emphasizing aesthetic considerations over social values"	art movement
African art	"modern and historical aesthetic, material, oral/audio and visual culture native to or originating from indigenous Africans or the African continent"	geographical
Ancient art	"art of the advanced cultures of ancient societies"	time period
Altar	"structure upon which offerings such as sacrifices are made for religious purposes"	physical structure

Table 02

This discrepancy may be one of the reasons that “the model mostly gets less accurate as it tries to predict concepts from the bottom of the tree (L3 to L5)” (Automated concept tagging for OpenAlex, n.d., p. 12).

Moving from hierarchical to semantic discrepancies, there are many concepts in OpenAlex that do not have attributed definitions, or have inaccurate definitions. For example, *Modern literature-L2* is defined as a “Wikimedia disambiguation page” (OpenAlex). These types of inaccuracies affect the quality of indexing, in turn negatively impacting the system's ability to retrieve work. Further, without consistently accurate definitions, indexing inaccuracies related to synonymy and homonymy are likely to arise.

Finally, there are many concepts in OpenAlex that are simply ineffective index terms. They can be too broad and will arise in many contexts, such as the concept *Wish* (L2). *Wish* is likely to pull content that is unrelated or too vaguely related. Likewise, there are concepts that may not be ineffective by themselves, but are placed too early in the hierarchy to adequately understand how they correlate to their parent concepts. This is apparent in the concept *New woman-L2* defined as a “late 19th-century feminist ideal; an educated, independent woman” (OpenAlex) and found under *Literature-L1*. This concept would be better suited farther down the hierarchy, potentially classified under a feminism-related parent concept.

Overall, this qualitative analysis identifies several challenges within the OpenAlex classification system. Most notably, there is a clear lack of correlation between the levels and between concepts in the same level leading to a potential loss in retrieval accuracy. Equally, missing and inaccurate information negatively impacts the functionality of the system as a whole. A restructuring of the higher (L0-L2) levels as proposed herein may increase retrieval efficiency at the lower (L3-L5) levels.

3.1.b Quantitative Evaluation

The quantitative analysis of OpenAlex examines the numeric discrepancies in the works, concepts, concepts levels, and relevancy of concepts within OpenAlex. While qualitative analysis follows a similar path, quantitative analysis is equally important due to its use of sample sizes, evaluation of large data sets on Excel, and the comparison of the data on the OpenAlex API versus Excel. The methodology predominantly uses Excel to analyse the data from OpenAlex, which was retrieved in the fall of 2023, thus offering insights and recommendations specific to this time period. It is important to note that OpenAlex indexes new works daily, resulting in changing data sets. Therefore, this analysis will provide recommendations on how it can improve through its evolving nature.

Figure 4.0 Concepts located under *Art-L0* by Level (Query 1)

Figure 4.1 Concepts located under *Art-L0* by Level (Query 2)

Analysing the concepts by level is essential for evaluating the overall classification system since it demonstrates the depth and breadth of OpenAlex as an indexing system. OpenAlex starts at broad L0 concepts and progressively narrows down to specific L5 concepts; there is an expectation that as the classification system goes deeper, there would be more specific concepts at L5. Therefore, scrutinising the ratio of concepts at each level is crucial in evaluating OpenAlex's classification system. This analysis involved querying the API to identify the children under each level using parent concept *Art-L0* (**Figure 4.0**). Our findings contrast with Scheidsteger & Haunschild (2023) since the majority of concepts are concentrated at L2. Beyond L2, the concepts dissipate, creating a significant gap between the number of L2 concepts and L5 concepts. This gap is a consequence of the absence of hierarchy between concepts as discussed in the qualitative section.

A problem encountered in concept retrieval involved discrepancies in the number of results obtained from different API queries (using [https://api.openalex.org/concepts?filter=level:\[ENTER LEVEL\],ancestors.id:\[ENTER CONCEPT ID\].](https://api.openalex.org/concepts?filter=level:[ENTER LEVEL],ancestors.id:[ENTER CONCEPT ID].)) **Figure 4.0** depicts the concepts per level when OpenAlex was prompted to find the children concepts for *Art-L0*, while **Figure 4.1** illustrates the concepts per level when each L1 concept was searched for their respective L2, L3, L4 and L5 concepts. As shown, the *Art-L0* query retrieves a total of 1678 concepts, whereas the aggregated L1 queries pull 1355. In theory, the number of children should be the same, given that the L1 concepts have *Art-L0* as a parent concept. This inconsistency poses a challenge for the search quality and effectiveness of OpenAlex, since the API fails to consistently retrieve the same number of concepts per query. This leads to the possibility of pulling inconsistent works, and numbers of works, when using the same query.

Another problem within OpenAlex arises from the disparity in works count compared to the number of L2 concepts within each L1 concept. The alignment between works count and L2 concepts is crucial for the effectiveness of OpenAlex's classification system, since over half of the concepts are within L2. Despite the semantic and hierarchical challenges between each concept level, L2 concepts play a crucial role in accurately indexing all the

works under Art. It is assumed that the ratio of concepts should match the ratio of works under an L1 concept to accurately index the collection. Therefore, having an adequate number of concepts at L2 to match the works count is extremely important.

We discovered that *Humanities-L1* claimed the majority of works, accounting for 58% (17 million) of the works under *Art* (**Figure 5.0**). Consequently, one would expect *Humanities-L1* to have the highest number of L2 concepts; roughly half of the concepts. This was not the case: *Humanities-L1* serves as the parent concept of only 7% (70 concepts), and does not support half of the L2 concepts under *Art-L0* (**Figure 5.1**). Additionally, as shown in **Figure 6.0**, the L2 concepts under *Humanities-L1* are only supported by two L3 concepts, and no L4 or L5 concepts. This means that the classification of the 17 million works under the parent concepts of *Art-L0* and *Humanities-L1* rely on 72 concepts. Such a disparity poses a risk of indexing errors in the classification of works. The limited availability of concepts, along with the semantic and hierarchical errors described in the qualitative analysis highlight the presence of numerous inaccuracies in the classification of *Humanities-L1*.

Figure 5.0 (Above) Count of works indexed using L1 Concepts
Figure 5.1 (Below) Distribution of concepts per L1 Concept

Figure 6.0 Concept distribution, L2 to L4

Additional problems within the OpenAlex classification system reveal themselves when examining the relevancy assessment between children and parent concepts. While the qualitative portion covered many specific semantic and hierarchical problems between children and parent concepts, this quantitative assessment looks at the overarching relationships.

This assessment was fulfilled through the analysis of the relevance between the L2 concept definitions in OpenAlex to the L1 and L0 concept definitions in OpenAlex. To be deemed relevant to the parent concepts, a L2 concept has to align with both the definitions of the L1 and L0 concepts in OpenAlex. If it failed to match the parent concept definitions, it would be classified as either “not related,” “too broad,” “too specific,” or “no definition.” While all the categories are self-explanatory, flagging when a concept has “no definition” is very important since it questions why OpenAlex deems the concept relevant to its parent. Additionally, in many cases where OpenAlex lacks a definition, there is likely a definition available on WikiData (the source from which OpenAlex pulls its data).

We assessed the relevance between children and parent concepts in two steps. First, we performed a full evaluation on the L2 concepts under *Humanities-L1*. Then, we carried out a randomised study, sampling 10% of L2 concepts found under each L1 concept.

Humanities-L1 was selected for a comprehensive evaluation since it serves as the parent concept to 58% of the works under Art, and because it was feasible to review the relevance of 70 L2 concepts. By conducting a full review of *Humanities-L1*, it gauged the efficiency of the 70 concepts in classifying works and also identified any further issues that may arise.

Figure 7.0 Relevance of L2 concepts found under *Humanities-L1*

Figure 7.1 Relevance of 10% of L2 concepts randomly sampled from each L1 concept

Through this assessment, further problems were identified under *Humanities-L1*. As illustrated in **Figure 7.0**, only 23 out of the 70 available L2 concepts were relevant. The remaining 47 concepts were either not related, too broad, too specific, or had no definition. Therefore, the concepts available to a user searching OpenAlex would not only retrieve inaccurately indexed works, but also yield irrelevant results for their search.

This issue is further supported by the sample size analysis, where 51 concepts demonstrated some degree of irrelevance to the parent concept. Although it is promising to see that 49 concepts were relevant to the parent concept, it is important to note that this represents a randomised sample of 10% of the L2 concepts (**Figure 7.1**). The distribution of relevancy can vary between each L1 concept, as evident in the case of *Humanities-L1*, where 67% of the concepts were not relevant.

This quantitative analysis demonstrates that there are many flaws in the OpenAlex system. The uneven distribution of L2 concepts between L1 concepts, aggregation of concepts in L2, and the low relevancy rates between children and parent concepts collectively highlight substantial room for error within the classification system in *Art-L0*.

3.2. Evaluation of indexing

To evaluate OpenAlex’s indexing of *Art* concepts, a work assigned with the *Art history-L1* concept was assessed to determine its relevance to the work, and to compare the work’s other assigned OpenAlex concepts with the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) that were given to the work by human cataloguers at Harvard University (see **Table 03** for the OpenAlex concepts and their definitions, followed by the LCSH underneath). In this comparison, it is clear that human cataloguers assign much more specific and accurate subject terms. OpenAlex assigned 16 total concepts to the work, with 7 being related and 9 being unrelated to the work, while the Harvard record has five subject headings that are all relevant and specific to the work. Overall, the amount of concepts that correctly describe the work is comparable from both sources, however, having a large amount of incorrect concepts assigned to works like in the OpenAlex example will muddle search results for users searching with the concepts that are unrelated to the work, such as *Biochemistry-L1*. Additionally, some of the OpenAlex concepts are unrelated and even offensive, like the concept *Shit-L2*, found under *Art history-L1*. This concept does not seem useful to exist at all as an indexing term, and certainly does not make sense to fall under the L1 concept *Art history* in OpenAlex’s hierarchy. This work also reveals that not only is OpenAlex assigning inaccurate concepts to works, but also that it struggles with precision and homonyms. This can be seen in the use of the concept *Girl-L2*, which is very broad for the subject matter. Additionally, it appears that OpenAlex took the concept *Globe-L2* from the work’s summary: “...women of color from around the globe” (Amazon.com), however the definition in OpenAlex has an anatomical meaning rather than the intended geographical meaning.

Colonize This!: Young Women of Color on Today's Feminism

<https://api.openalex.org/works/W617169363>

Concept	Level	Relevant to work?	OpenAlex Definition/Explanation
Feminism	2	Y	"academic field of study in international politics"
White (mutation)	3	N	About sex-linked gene discovered in flies; definition: "Sex-linked mutation"
Gender studies	1	Y	"interdisciplinary academic field devoted to analysing gender identity and gendered representation"
Women of color	3	Y	"term for a woman considered non-white"
Globe	2	N	"part of the eyeball"

Girl	2	Y	“young female human”
Shit	2	N	"profane word referring to feces"
Sociology	0	Y	"scientific study of human society and its origins, development, organizations, and institutions"
History	0	Y	past events and their tracks or records, studied by various branches of human sciences of history
Race (biology)	2	Y	“biological concept”
Psychology	0	N	"scientific study of the way the human mind works and how it influences behaviour, or the influence of a particular person's character on their behaviour"
Art history	1	N	"academic study of objects of art in their historical development"
Developmental psychology	1	N	"scientific study of changes that occur in human beings over the course of their lives"
Biochemistry	1	N	"study of chemical processes in living organisms"
Chemistry	0	N	"branch of physical science concerned with the composition, structure and properties of matter"
Gene	2	N	Book is about social aspects of race, not genetics; definition: "basic physical and functional unit of heredity"

Table 03

Library of Congress subject headings in Harvard University's catalogue:

Feminism and racism -- United States

Third-wave feminism -- United States

Minority women -- United States -- Social conditions

Feminism

Minority women -- Social conditions

Another example, this time looking at a work that is relevant to art concepts, shows a similar pattern (**Table 04**). There are a total of 20 concepts assigned to the work, with 10 being relevant to the work and 10 being irrelevant. Of the 10 relevant concepts, some are quite broad, such as *Art-L0*, *Art History-L1*, *Archaeology-L1*, and *History-L0*. While these concepts are technically relevant to the work, they are too broad to be useful to describe it, as it is about a very specific subject. Again, since half of the concepts are unrelated to the work, this would cause problems in the search results for anyone using those unrelated concepts. Meanwhile, there are 5 Library of Congress Subject Headings in the Harvard record that are all relevant and specific to this work, with one that is actually the proper name of the object

that the work is about (Derveni krater). This would help immensely for anyone using subject headings to find this work, or works related to it.

The Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) is another vocabulary that can be used as a point of comparison for OpenAlex’s *Art* concepts. The AAT contains an entry for “volute kraters,” described as: “(kraters, vessels (containers), ... Furnishings and Equipment (hierarchy name)) Note: Kraters with volute-shaped handles extending from the shoulders to above the rim. They are rare in black-figure but common in red-figure” (Getty, n.d.). This is a more accurate and descriptive subject term than OpenAlex can offer with *Volute-L3*, which is just one part of the object being described in this work. Additionally, the OpenAlex parents of *Volute-L3* are not related to art. The L3 concept falls under *Inlet-L2*, which falls under *Mechanical engineering-L1*, in turn leading to *Engineering-L0*, which are not relevant to this work but are included in its assigned concepts. OpenAlex does have concepts assigned to this work that describe the material (*Bronze-L2*) and its features (*Iconography-L2*), but these concepts are quite broad if not used with any other facets. Additionally, the concept *Macedonian-L2* in OpenAlex describes the contemporary language, not the ancient Thessalian language that is actually inscribed on the krater. This concept would fit the work better if it were referring to Macedonian culture or history, not the contemporary language. More accurate terms in Wikidata exist, such as “Ancient Macedonian” (Q35974) which notably has a *different from* field for “Macedonian,” the concept used for this work, or “Macedonia” (Q83958) with the definition “ancient Greek kingdom,” which more accurately describes the cultural/archaeological context for the object. Interestingly, Wikidata also has an entry for Derveni krater (Q3002227). However, these Wikidata entries do not exist as concepts in OpenAlex, limiting its ability to apply accurate index terms. As highlighted in this example, OpenAlex comes close to assigning relevant concepts, but the definition of the concepts available may not actually suit the work. Additionally, both the AAT and LCSH contain index terms that more accurately suit the specificity that is required when describing works about art objects.

The Derveni krater : masterpiece of classical Greek metalwork

<https://api.openalex.org/works/W594641071>

Concept	Level	Relevant to work?	OpenAlex Definition
Volute	3	Y	curved funnel that increases in area as it approaches the discharge port; casing in a centrifugal pump that receives the fluid being pumped by the impeller, maintaining the velocity of the fluid through to the diffuser
Iconography	2	Y	use of symbols, themes, and subject matter in the visual arts
Frieze	2	Y	wide central section part of an entablature

Macedonian	2	N	South Slavic language mostly spoken in North Macedonia and its neighbouring countries
Bronze	2	Y	Metal alloy
Context (archaeology)	2	N	glossary for archaeological terms
Art	0	Y	field of work focused on creating expressive work intended to be appreciated for its beauty or emotional power (use Q838948 for the resulting work)
Anecdote	2	N	remarkable or characteristic story
Index (typography)	2	N	punctuation mark (note: definition in Wikidata is for “manicule” which is an index finger pointing symbol and is also known as “index” in typography)
Ancient history	1	Y	human history from the earliest records to the end of the classical periods
Classics	1	Y	study of classical antiquity such as ancient Greece and ancient Rome
Art history	1	Y	academic study of objects of art in their historical development
Literature	1	N	polysemous term referring to a written art form, and the set of all literary works
Archaeology	1	Y	study of the past via material culture
History	0	Y	past events and their tracks or records
Engineering	0	N	applied science
Mechanical engineering	1	N	engineering discipline
World Wide Web	1	N	global system of interlinked hypertext documents accessed via the Internet
Computer science	0	N	study of computation
Inlet	2	N	in coastal geography, an indentation of a shoreline that often leads to an enclosed body of salt water, such as a sound, bay, lagoon, or marsh

Table 04

Library of Congress subject headings in Harvard University's catalogue:

Derveni krater

Bronzes, Greek -- Greece -- Dervéni

Vases, Classical -- Greece -- Dervéni

Vases, Greek -- Greece -- Dervéni

Dervéni (Greece) -- Antiquities

For a wider view of how relevant OpenAlex concepts are to the works they are assigned to, two L2 concepts and one L3 concept were chosen for analysis. The OpenAlex API was queried (using [https://api.openalex.org/works?filter=concepts.id:\[ENTER CONCEPT ID\]&sample=15&per-page=15](https://api.openalex.org/works?filter=concepts.id:[ENTER CONCEPT ID]&sample=15&per-page=15)) for a random sample of 15 works that were assigned with each concept. Then, the works were grouped by whether they were relevant or not relevant to the concept, with a third group for works that were not in English labelled as 'language barrier.' Specific concepts were chosen to more clearly measure if they are relevant or not to the articles we sampled. The relevancy of the concepts to the works was based on the definition given by OpenAlex, supplied by Wikidata. The three chosen concepts were *Defamiliarization-L2* (**Figure 8.0**), *Mythology-L2* (**Figure 8.1**), and *Happening-L3* (**Figure 8.2**). For *Mythology* 67% of works were not related to the concept, and 13% of works were related. For the concept *Happening* 79% of the works were not related and only 7% were related. Conversely, for *Defamiliarization* 80% of the works were related to the concept. These samples show that there can be quite a variance in the relevance and accuracy of OpenAlex concepts assigned to works.

Figure 8.0 (Above) Count of relevant works indexed with *Defamiliarization-L2*

Figure 8.1 (Below) Count of relevant works indexed with *Mythology-L2*

Figure 8.2 Count of relevant works indexed with *Happening-L3*

Both of these approaches demonstrate the potential for high amounts of inaccuracies when it comes to OpenAlex’s concepts being used as index terms for works, in part due to issues with homonyms or similar concepts, lack of specificity, illogical concept hierarchies, or simply choosing irrelevant words from titles and abstracts.

Figure 9.0 Concept level distribution of 15 sampled articles

Furthermore, this report also analysed the indexed concepts by level for the 15 sampled works under *Mythology-L2*. This was done by taking all the concepts associated with each of the 15 sampled articles used for the relevancy analysis and separating it by level, to see which levels OpenAlex uses to index its works. This analysis demonstrates that 15 articles aggregately used 183 concepts for indexing which, as previously demonstrated, are not all relevant or accurate to the work. **Figure 9.0** highlights how the 15 sample articles mostly used L0, L1, and L2 indexing concepts, and used the least L3 concepts. There were no L4 or L5 concepts used for indexing. The use of broad L0 to L2 concepts may be a

consequence of not having enough L4 and L5 concepts within OpenAlex, which limits the automated indexing system from using more specific concepts. Consequently, OpenAlex is forced to use broad L0 concepts - like *Art*, *History* and *Philosophy* - to index its works, which leads to many inaccuracies in information retrieval and classification.

4 Conclusion

OpenAlex has an impressive ability to index a high volume of works due to its automated tagging system. While this is a compelling step forward in the realm of open access work and automated systems, there is significant progress to be made to ensure that OpenAlex is a functional tool that researchers can use to their benefit. The qualitative analysis demonstrates that hierarchical and semantic discrepancies increase classification inaccuracies, and suggests possible edits to be made to increase the effectiveness of the concept structure. The quantitative analysis demonstrates numeric discrepancies and concludes that the system leaves substantial room for error. The evaluation of indexing indicates that works are often indexed inaccurately, and do not compare in accuracy to human-indexed works. This leads to low retrieval accuracy and affects the usability of OpenAlex for research.

Recommendations gathered from this paper involve several approaches. A restructuring of concepts from L0 to L5 should be considered, with the goal of logically redistributing concepts so that they are not bottlenecked at L2. This redistribution would also, ideally, solve the discrepancies presented in the quantitative analysis. Further, futile index concepts should be removed from the system, and all remaining concepts should be verified to have accurate definitions in the OpenAlex API and UI. Additionally, a solution is required for the frequent errors OpenAlex makes with synonyms and homonyms. This would help reduce the amount of irrelevant concepts assigned to works and increase the retrieval accuracy of the system.

Overall, the efforts of OpenAlex in creating an open access database are notable, and have created a starting point to encourage discussion and innovation in open access classification and in the use of automation for classification. OpenAlex is attempting to fill a large academic gap as an open access automated tagging system. With attention, time, and new tools as they become available, the logistical challenges presented herein can be resolved, and OpenAlex can expand to bridge this gap.

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